

EFFECT OF MATURITY LEVELS AND SPERMINE ON BIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES AT LOW TEMPERATURE STORAGE OF PAPAYA CV. RED LADY TAIWAN

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MS Received: 15.11.2024; MS Revised:28.12.2024; MS Accepted:29.12.2024)

MS 3329

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE)

Abstract

An experiment was conducted at the Department of Fruit Science and Department of Post Harvest Technology of ASPEE College of Horticulture and Forestry, Navsari Agriculture University, Navsari during December 2014 and April 2015. The experiment comprised of harvesting papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan at three different maturity stages (Colour break stage, 50% yellow and 75% yellow stage), dipping them in aqueous solutions of spermine (0.0, 1.0 and 2.0 mM) and storing them at ambient as well as $12 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ temperature. The eighteen treatments were evaluated in a Completely Randomized with Factorial Concept (FCRD) and replicated three times. Results indicated a significant impact of maturity levels on all parameters included in the study. Postharvest application of spermine had a significant influence on all traits studied in this investigation. Whereas, total soluble solids, total sugar, reducing sugar and non reducing sugar were found maximum in fruits harvested at seventy five percent maturity. The highest values of TSS, total sugars, reducing sugars, non reducing sugars, titrable acidity and ascorbic acid content were found with spermine @ 2.0 mM. The fruits stored at low temperature having long perishability as compared to stored at room temperature.

Keywords - Harvesting papaya, maturity stages, Eighteen treatments, stored at room temperature.

Introduction

Papaya is native to tropical America and is believed to have originated from South America (De Candolle, 1884). It was introduced in India in the early part of the 16th century from Philippines through Malaysia (Schroeder, 1958). It belongs to the family Caricaceae which consists of six relatively small genera. Papaya is highly appreciated worldwide for its flavour, nutritional qualities, digestive properties and serotonin content (Fernandes *et al.*, 2006). Papaya is a good source of serotonin (0.99 mg/100 mg), which has been associated with enabling the gut to mediate reflex activity and also decreasing the risk of thrombosis (Santiago-Silva *et al.*, 2011). Leaves of *Carica papaya* are able to remove stains. Papain has milk clotting (rennet) and protein digesting properties. A piece of raw papaya is often added, when preparing meat. The papain present in raw papaya not only reduces the time taken for cooking meat but also makes the meat very tender. Value added products like juice, blended beverages, jam, jelly, *petha*, *tuty phooty*, dehydrated, osmo dried, cereal flakes, fruit bar, candy, restructured and intermediate moisture and frozen products can be developed from fresh papaya fruits. The pectin content in papaya fruits facilitates jam preparation and easy setting. Gujarat is the second largest producer of papaya in the country.

Material And Methods

The experiment was carried out during December 2014 and April 2015 at the Department of Post Harvest Technology, ASPEE College of Horticulture and Forestry, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, which is situated on the coast of Arabian sea at $20^\circ-57'$ N latitude and $72^\circ-54'$ longitude at an altitude of about 10-12 meters above the mean sea level. The campus is 13 km away from Dandi, a historical place near the Arabian seashore.

Treatment Details**Factor- 1 (Maturity stages)**M₁- Colour break stage (25% yellow)M₂- ½ of the skin is yellow (50% yellow)M₃- ¾ of the skin is yellow (75% yellow)**Factor-2 (Spermine treatments)**S₀ - 0.0 mM spermineS₁ - 1.0 mM spermineS₂ - 2.0 mM spermine**Factor- 3 (Storage Temperature)**T₁ - Ambient Temperature (December-2014 26.2°C and April-2015 27.2°C)T₂ - Low Temperature ($12 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$)

Uniformly sized papaya fruits harvested at different maturity stages were dipped in aqueous solutions of spermine for 5 minutes and dried for 30 minutes at room temperature and packed in rigid plastic crates and kept at a temperature of $12 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ as well as room temperature.

Observations Recorded

Bio-chemical observations like TSS (°Brix), Total sugars (%), Reducing sugars (%), Non-reducing sugars (%), Titrable acidity (%) and Ascorbic acid (mg/100 g of fruit) are working out by various specific methods of each parameter (Ranganna, 1986).

The data collected were analyzed statistically as per the procedure appropriate for Completely Randomized Design with Factorial Concept (FCRD). The treatment means were compared by means of critical differences at 5 per cent level of probability and the data was analyzed statistically (Panse and Sukhatme, 1967).

Results And Discussion**Effect of maturity levels**

Table 1 revealed a significant influence of different maturity levels on the TSS of papaya in cv. Red Lady Taiwan. Total soluble solids were maximum in 75% mature papaya fruits on the 8th day of storage. Total soluble solids exhibited an increasing trend as the maturity level increased. This can be attributed to higher respiration rates in seventy five percent mature fruits and subsequent conversion of starch into sugars. These data are similar to those of Serry *et al.* (2011) in papaya, Rahman *et al.* (2014) in strawberry, Alhassan *et al.* (2014) in sweet orange cv. Late Valencia and Gonge *et al.* (2014) in banana as they too recorded higher TSS in fully mature fruits.

Significant differences were observed in reducing sugars, non reducing sugars and total sugars in different maturity levels (Table 1 and 2). The maximum reducing sugars, non reducing sugars and total sugars was observed in 75% mature fruits on the 8th day of storage. Reducing sugars, non-reducing sugars and total sugars showed an increment with an increase in maturity levels. The observed increment in total sugars could be due to hydrolysis of starch into sugar as ripening progressed. This is in agreement with the findings of Rahman *et al.* (2014) in strawberry and Gonge *et al.* (2014) in banana.

There was a significant effect of maturity levels on the titrable acidity on the 8th day of storage in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan (Table 3). Titrable acidity progressively decreased as the fruits ripened. Titrable acidity was the maximum in 25% mature fruits on the 8th day of storage. Higher titrable acidity in immature fruits was earlier reported by Serry *et al.* (2011) in papaya, Rahman *et al.* (2014) in strawberry and Gonge *et al.* (2014) in banana.

Maturity levels had a significant influence on the ascorbic acid in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan on the 8th day of storage (Table 3). Ascorbic acid was the maximum in 25% mature fruits on the 8th day of storage. Ascorbic acid exhibited a declining trend with the advancement in fruit maturity. Mannose and L-galactose are key substrates for ascorbic acid synthesis in plants. Therefore cell wall degradation during ripening may provide substrates for ascorbic acid synthesis, leading to an increase in ascorbic acid. In previous studies similar results were reported by Bron and Jacomino (2006), Serry *et al.* (2011) and Rahman *et al.* (2014).

Effect of spermine

Total soluble solids were significantly maximum in papaya fruits subjected to 2.0 mM spermine treatment on the 8th day of storage (Table 1). The reason for the increase in TSS could be attributed to the water loss and hydrolysis of starch and other polysaccharides into soluble forms of sugar (Ullah and Javandha, 2014). Wills *et al.* (1980) also reported that starch gets hydrolyzed into mono and disaccharides, which in turn may lead to an increase in TSS. The results on TSS in the present studies are in agreement with the findings of Malik *et al.* (2006) and Bhat *et al.* (2014) in mango and Champa *et al.* (2015) in grapes.

The maximum reducing sugars, non reducing sugars and total sugars was observed in spermine @ 2.0 mM treatment was found significant on the 8th day of storage (Table 1 and 2). The increase in sugars during storage may possibly be due to the breakdown of complex organic metabolites into simple molecules or due to the hydrolysis of starch into sugars (Wills *et al.*, 1980, Prashant and Masoodi, 2009). The findings of Malik and Singh (2004 and 2006) in mango are in agreement with these results.

There was a significant effect of spermine on the titrable acidity on the 8th day of storage in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan (Table 3). Titrable acidity was the maximum in 2.0 mM spermine treatment on the 8th day of storage. The maintenance of higher acidity in spermine treated fruits may be due to the decreased hydrolysis of organic acids and subsequent accumulation of organic acids which were oxidised at lower rate because of decreased respiration (Rhodes *et al.*, 1968 and Pool *et al.*, 1972). Zokaee *et al.* (2007) and Ishaq *et al.* (2009) suggested that titrable acidity decreases could be due to consumption of organic acids in fruits during respiration. Similar results were reported by Malik and Singh (2004 and 2006) in mango and Champa *et al.* (2015) in grape.

Significant influence of spermine was found on the ascorbic acid on the 8th day of storage in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan (Table 3). Ascorbic acid was the maximum in 2.0 mM spermine treatment on the 8th day of storage. Application of spermine may have inhibited ascorbate oxydase activity, which is responsible for the degradation of ascorbic acid (Malik *et al.*, 2006). Malik and Singh (2006) also observed higher ascorbic acid in mango fruits treated with polyamines.

Effect of temperature

Table 1 revealed a significant influence of storage temperature on TSS of papaya in cv. Red Lady Taiwan. Total soluble solids were higher in fruits stored at room temperature on the 8th day of storage. The increase in total soluble solids was the outcome of conversion of carbohydrates into simple sugars through a complex mechanism during storage and the conversion rate increases with an increase in temperature (Thin *et al.*, 2013). Premlata (2009), Shakila and Anburani (2010) and Bariya (2012) in papaya; Kelani *et al.* (2010) in mango; Arnal and Rio (2013) in persimmon and Ahmad *et al.* (2001) in banana also recorded greater TSS at higher temperatures.

Significant differences were observed in reducing sugars, non reducing sugars and total sugars at different storage temperature (Table 1 and 2). Higher reducing sugars, non reducing sugars and total sugars were observed in fruits storage at room temperature on the 8th day of storage. The accumulation of reducing sugars is a function of starch metabolism which is slower in fruits stored at low temperature and this may have resulted in lower reducing sugars. The total sugars were greater at ambient temperature due to higher rate of hydrolysis and higher rate of respiration. The findings of Premlata (2009), Shakila and Anburani (2010) and Bariya (2012) in papaya; Vishnuprasanna *et al.* (2000) and Mulla (2008) in custard apple and Patel *et al.* (2010) in sapota are in line with above results.

There was a significant effect of storage temperature on the titrable acidity on the 8th day of storage in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan (Table 3). Higher titrable acidity was observed in fruits stored at 12+1°C temperature on the 8th day of the storage. This might be due to delayed ripening at low temperature and utilization of acids in respiratory process or due to suppression of ethylene formation which is responsible for ripening process. These findings are in close proximity with the findings of Alam *et al.* (2010) and Bariya (2012) in papaya;

Thin *et al.* (2013) and Kelany *et al.* (2010) in mango and Patel *et al.* (2010) in sapota.

Significant effect of storage temperature was found on the ascorbic acid on the 8th day of storage in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan (Table 3). Ascorbic acid was higher in cold stored fruits on the 8th day of storage. Ascorbic acid is an important nutrient quality factor which is very sensitive to degradation due to its oxidation. Higher ascorbic acid in cold stored fruits may be due to the suppression of ascorbate oxidase activities at low temperature. Caron *et al.* (2013) in papaya; Hossain *et al.* (2014), Malik and Khan (2005) and Kelany *et al.* (2010) in mango; Tembo *et al.* (2008) in ber and Patel *et al.* (2010) in sapota are in agreement with the above findings.

Conclusion

There was a significant influence of maturity levels on all attributes considered for this trial. Seventy five percent mature fruits had the maximum values for total soluble solids, total sugars, reducing sugars and non reducing sugars on the 8th day of storage. The maximum total soluble solids, total sugars, reducing sugars, non reducing sugars, titrable acidity and ascorbic acid were observed in the treatment comprising 2.0 mM spermine on the 8th day of storage. Storage at 12±1°C temperature resulted in the highest titrable acidity and ascorbic acid content after 8th days of storage. Whereas, total soluble solids, total sugars, reducing sugars, non reducing sugars were the highest in fruits stored at room temperature on the 8th day of storage.

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Table 1. Effect of maturity levels, spermine and low temperature on TSS (^o Brix) and Total sugar (%) of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan.

Treatments	TSS (^o Brix)						Total sugar (%)					
	4 th day			8 th day			4 th day			8 th day		
	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled
Maturity levels												
M₁	5.89	5.74	5.81	9.82	9.95	9.86	4.83	4.94	4.88	5.30	5.61	5.85
M₂	8.41	8.48	8.47	11.91	12.02	11.94	5.65	5.52	5.58	6.35	6.23	6.29
M₃	10.68	10.53	10.62	12.82	12.96	12.87	6.03	5.96	5.98	6.90	6.79	6.84
S. Em. ±	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.047	0.045	0.046	0.037	0.033	0.024	0.038	0.044	0.029
CD at 5%	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.09	0.07	0.11	0.13	0.08

Spermine												
S ₀	8.28	8.07	8.17	11.30	11.38	11.34	5.24	5.13	5.18	5.74	5.67	5.70
S ₁	8.31	8.37	8.34	11.58	11.67	11.62	5.98	5.84	5.91	6.48	6.36	6.42
S ₂	8.34	8.41	8.36	11.67	11.83	11.75	6.34	6.23	6.28	7.10	6.93	7.01
S. Em. ±	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.047	0.045	0.046	0.037	0.033	0.020	0.038	0.044	0.024
CD at 5%	0.13	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.11	0.13	0.07
Temperature												
T ₁	9.45	9.63	9.54	12.63	12.78	12.70	6.10	5.91	6.00	7.22	7.03	7.12
T ₂	7.14	7.29	7.21	10.42	10.55	10.53	5.40	5.23	5.31	6.15	6.05	6.10
S. Em. ±	0.03	0.027	0.020	0.04	0.036	0.026	0.03	0.027	0.020	0.03	0.036	0.024
CD at 5%	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.11	0.10	0.07	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.10	0.07
CV %	2.07	2.05	2.04	1.71	1.63	1.66	3.00	2.45	2.80	2.94	3.44	3.18
Interaction												
T×M	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.19	0.18	0.19	0.15	0.13	0.10	0.16	0.18	0.12
T×S	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.19	0.18	0.18	0.15	0.13	0.10	0.16	0.18	0.12
M×S	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.23	0.22	0.21	0.18	0.16	0.12	0.19	0.22	0.14
T×M×S	0.28	0.28	0.28	0.33	0.31	0.32	0.26	0.23	0.17	0.27	0.31	0.20

Table 2. Effect of maturity levels, spermine and low temperature on reducing sugars (%) and non-reducing sugars (%) of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan.

Treatments	Reducing sugars (%)						Non-reducing sugars (%)					
	4 th day			8 th day			4 th day			8 th day		
	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled
Maturity levels												
M ₁	3.31	3.40	3.36	3.55	3.76	3.65	1.52	1.64	1.58	1.75	1.85	1.80
M ₂	3.61	3.34	3.47	4.05	3.83	3.94	2.04	2.18	2.11	2.30	2.40	2.35
M ₃	3.78	3.57	3.67	4.47	4.25	4.36	2.25	2.39	2.32	2.43	2.54	2.49
S. Em. ±	0.021	0.022	0.015	0.035	0.029	0.023	0.016	0.019	0.012	0.017	0.016	0.012
CD at 5%	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.10	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.03
Spermine												
S ₀	3.35	3.10	3.22	3.65	3.44	3.54	1.89	2.03	1.96	2.09	2.21	2.15
S ₁	4.05	3.79	3.92	4.34	4.11	4.22	1.93	2.05	1.99	2.14	2.25	2.19
S ₂	4.35	4.10	4.22	4.84	4.60	4.72	1.99	2.13	2.06	2.26	2.33	2.30
S. Em. ±	0.021	0.022	0.012	0.035	0.029	0.018	0.016	0.019	0.010	0.017	0.016	0.010
CD at 5%	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.03
Temperature												
T ₁	4.08	3.77	3.92	4.94	4.66	4.80	2.02	2.14	2.08	2.28	2.37	2.32
T ₂	3.54	3.24	3.39	4.01	3.89	3.95	1.86	1.99	1.93	2.05	2.16	2.10
S. Em. ±	0.02	0.018	0.012	0.03	0.023	0.018	0.01	0.015	0.010	0.01	0.013	0.010
CD at 5%	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03
CV %	2.68	2.71	2.68	4.28	3.52	3.90	3.55	2.11	2.70	3.38	3.08	3.21
Interaction												
T×M	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.14	0.12	0.09	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.05
T×S	0.09	0.06	0.06	0.14	0.08	0.09	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.05
M×S	0.10	0.11	0.07	0.18	0.14	0.11	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.06
T×M×S	0.15	0.12	0.10	0.25	0.20	0.16	0.11	0.13	0.08	0.12	0.12	0.08

Table 3. Effect of maturity levels, spermine and low temperature on Titrable acidity (%) and Ascorbic acid (mg/100g of fruit) of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan.

Treatments	Titrable acidity (%)						Ascorbic acid (mg/100g of fruit)					
	4 th day			8 th day			4 th day			8 th day		
	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled
Maturity levels												
M ₁	3.80	3.75	3.77	3.27	3.23	3.25	30.33	32.23	31.28	24.95	23.70	24.32
M ₂	3.66	3.61	3.64	3.16	3.12	3.14	25.86	27.93	26.89	22.77	21.88	22.32
M ₃	3.46	3.51	3.48	3.06	3.02	3.04	28.79	27.03	27.91	20.94	21.44	21.19
S. Em. ±	0.018	0.019	0.013	0.013	0.014	0.009	0.050	0.068	0.059	0.109	0.070	0.089
CD at 5%	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.14	0.19	0.16	0.31	0.20	0.25
Spermine												
S ₀	3.61	3.56	3.59	3.11	3.07	3.09	27.47	25.64	26.55	21.51	23.21	22.36
S ₁	3.83	3.78	3.80	3.29	3.25	3.27	29.11	28.40	28.75	24.17	23.27	23.95
S ₂	4.01	3.96	3.98	3.45	3.41	3.43	31.39	29.23	30.31	25.98	24.84	25.41
S. Em. ±	0.018	0.019	0.011	0.013	0.014	0.008	0.050	0.068	0.057	0.109	0.070	0.089

CD at 5%	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.14	0.19	0.16	0.31	0.20	0.25
Temperature												
T₁	2.59	2.49	2.54	1.67	1.59	1.63	27.35	25.16	26.25	22.88	21.30	22.09
T₂	3.25	3.32	3.28	1.89	1.81	1.85	33.29	30.63	31.96	24.76	22.36	23.56
S. Em. ±	0.02	0.016	0.011	0.01	0.011	0.008	0.04	0.055	0.045	0.094	0.057	0.029
CD at 5%	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.12	0.16	0.14	0.25	0.16	0.20
CV %	2.05	2.14	2.08	1.14	1.19	1.16	3.75	3.51	3.63	2.07	2.33	2.20
Interaction												
T×M	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.20	0.27	0.24	0.44	0.28	0.36
T×S	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.20	0.27	0.24	0.44	0.28	0.36
M×S	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.05	0.25	0.34	0.29	0.54	0.35	0.44
T×M×S	0.07	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.06	0.35	0.48	0.42	0.76	0.49	0.63